

THE METHOD OF HOUSING AND UTILITY SERVICES PROVIDERS' DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS' MANAGEMENT TEAM COMPETENCIES' DEVELOPMENT*Chernenko Y.**Chairman of the Board of Directors,
MASTERGAZ LLC, Kyiv, Ukraine***Abstract**

This study proposes a new method to develop management team competencies for development projects of housing and utility services providers. Based on the analysis of previous works, the need to improve the efficiency of the development projects' management team of housing and communal services providers due to the competencies required. Certain approaches are proposed.

Keywords: provider of housing and communal services, development project, project team, competencies, development, risk management.

Introduction. The dynamic development of engineering and technologies requires humans to constantly update and improve knowledge and skills, develop personalities, and improve competencies [1, 2]. One of the main aspects of such development is the growth of high-tech activities and the strengthening of the innovative orientation of enterprises. Due to the fact that the field of housing and communal services requires not only the provision of high-quality housing and communal services but also effective and quick problem-solving solutions that arise in the process of customer service, therefore it also requires the staff to constantly develop: update knowledge and skills [3].

Review of publications on the topic. The success of the development projects' management of housing and communal services providers (HCSP) depends on timely and high-quality risk management. In work [4], a conceptual model of risk management of development projects in HCSP was described, taking to consideration the identified features of the management of these projects [5].

In [6], the author developed a methodology for integrated management of deviations in projects, which enabled the project manager to manage all the causes of deviations (risks, changes, problems, conflicts, stresses, crises) in a project in an integrated, systematic manner. The results of this study provide tools for the development of models and methods of risk management of development projects but do not consider the peculiarities of HCSPs.

In works [7, 8], the author proposed some models of integrated risk management of scientific project conflicts in the conditions of behavioral economics, in particular, a conceptual model built on the basis of the "Iceberg of Change Management" model, which made it possible to integrate such methodologies as: project management, stakeholder theory, risk management, HR management, conflict theory, behavioral economics.

In addition, system and cognitive models make it possible to assess the impact of various factors, in particular personnel risks, conflicts and factors of behavioral economics on each other and on the scientific project as a whole. These studies are an example of how it is possible to integrate approaches to the management of the development project team of the HCSP, as well as to evaluate the impact of various factors on it.

In works [9, 10] authors promoted models and methods of forming teams of educational projects of

professional development, in particular, developed a conceptual model of parameters of creativity and personnel risks of team members of the specified projects; a mathematical model for determining the "degree of trust" of team members, which makes it possible to evaluate the parameters of creativity and personnel risks of team members of such projects, as well as the method of forming teams taking into account the parameters of creativity and personnel risks of members of such teams. The results of these studies provide tools for the development of indicators for assessing the effectiveness of the competencies of members of the development project teams of the HCSPs.

Risk management of development projects of HCSPs should contribute to the improvement of the management efficiency of these projects due to the implementation of: automation of management and algorithmizing of decision-making processes; prototyping possible alternative solutions; A/B testing and choosing the best solution; introduction of a process approach to risk management and decision-making; building a dynamic organizational structure for management of development projects; implementation of benchmarking [5, 11]. From the above, it follows that, in particular, at the stage of building a dynamic organizational structure of development project management, there is a need to improve the effectiveness of team management due to the development of personnel competencies to ensure successful planning and implementation of the specified projects.

The aim of this study is to develop the method of the HCSP's management team competencies' development.

Results and discussion. In accordance with the conceptual model of HCSPs' development projects' risk management [4] and the improved method of forming a dynamic organizational structure for the management of specified projects [11], we can admit second most important component (after modernization of the HCSP's organizational structure), in author's view – participants' competencies improvement (fig. 1).

Competence [12, 13] is the personal ability of a specialist to solve a certain class of professional tasks. Competence also means formally described requirements for company employees' personal, professional, etc. qualities. In this sense, competence is used in personnel evaluation.

Fig. 1. Scheme of HCSP's development projects' management team's competencies' development

Competence is a set of powers; availability of knowledge and experience necessary for effective activity in a given subject area.

A competency model is a set of types of competencies required to successfully perform a specific job in a specific organization. The model of competence can include various knowledge, abilities, skills, and individual characteristics. The main requirement for them is - they should be described in the form of behavior indicators [12, 14].

The main thing for the formation of a specialist's competence is specialized education. The acquired practical knowledge and skills complement the initial level of competence. All this can be imagined in the form of a formula, that is, competence = know + can + want + do.

Modern companies, as a rule, consider competence as an important tool [13, 14] for:

a) measuring the future potential performance of candidates;

b) analysis of abilities, potential, and productivity of employees.

In relation to an official, competence is a set of rights and powers.

The method of HCSP's development projects' management team's competencies' development includes the following stages (fig. 2):

1. Setting goals and objectives for the HCSP's development projects' management team's competencies' development.

2. Formation of a group of experts who will collect and analyze the information.

3. Collection of information on the development of competencies and their analysis.

4. Development of reference job profiles and team competencies' model. At this stage, you can use the methods listed in [12, 13, 15].

5. Selection of performance criteria for analyzing the abilities and potential of the members of the HCSP's development project team.

Fig 2. The method of HCSP's development projects' management team's competencies' development

6. Verification of the validity of the reference job profiles and the model of the team's competencies. If it does not satisfy the efficiency criteria, then go to point 4. If it does, then go to point 7.

7. Implementation of reference profiles of positions and team's competencies' model in the management of development projects of HCSPs.

8. Development of recommendations for the development of competencies of the team members of the HCSP's development projects. This process is gradual and continuous and consists of the formation of professional competence, it can be divided into the following stages:

- obtaining a special education;
- acquisition of practical knowledge and skills, in particular solving practical joint tasks in a dynamic mode with the aim of developing skills to interact in a team;
- professional development, taking special courses, trainings, and reading special literature;
- gaining professional experience, in particular, on-the-job training thanks to the experience of others;
- achieving professionalism in one's field by performing special developmental tasks aimed at increasing the level of competence.

9. Assessment of competence of team members. This stage should be regular, independent, purposeful, and transparent, with criteria understandable to employees.

When evaluating the competence of employees, it is necessary to rely on behavior indicators. It is they who make it clear what competence and power mean, the differences.

The author proposes the following scale of competence development:

- 0 – competence not detected / absent;
- 1 – the level of basic development;
- 2 – the level of confident possession of competence in standard situations;
- 3 – master level (benchmark, possibility of scaling).

If it does not meet the efficiency criteria, then go to point 8. If it does, then go to point 10.

10. The competence of the members of the HCSP's development projects' management team corresponds to the reference profiles of the positions and the competencies' model.

Thus, the method of developing the competencies of the project management team of housing and utility service providers has shown promise. The developed approach to the development of the team's competencies will allow the managers of the specified projects to increase the efficiency of their management by implementing them into the practical activities of the HCSPs.

Results and discussion. The proposed method of HCSP's development projects' management team's

competencies' development, which is based on the development of the competencies of the team members and the assessment of their effectiveness, allows to:

- significantly improve the professionalism of the team;
- crystallize the mission and strategy of the HCSP;
- better define consumer values and increase the level of clients trust;
- improve corporate culture and labor standards;
- minimize the shortage and flow of personnel in development projects due to professional selection and correct competence, as well as start the process of training the personnel reserve;
- deploy a full-fledged project approach in the activities of the HCSP;
- improve communications within the HCSP, coordinate participants' actions, and optimize work at all stages thanks to conscious experience;
- ensure a more conscious and effective process of uncertainty (risk) management.

References

1. Bushuyev, S., Bushuiev, D., Yaroshenko, R. (2018). Breakthrough competencies in the management of innovative projects and programs. *Bulletin of NTU «KhPI». Series: Strategic Management, Portfolio, Program and Project Management*, 1 (1277), 3–9.
2. Bushuyev, S., Bushuiev, D. (2017). Emotional Intelligence – The Driver of Development of Breakthrough Competences of the Project. *Proceedings 30th IPMA World Congress – Breakthrough competences for managing change*. Astana, Kazakhstan, 8–14.
3. International Project Management Association (2015). *Individual Competence Baseline for Project, Programme & Portfolio Management (4th Ed.)*, 415.
4. Chernenko, Yu. V., Danchenko, O. B., Melenchuk, V. M. (2022). Conceptual model of risk management in development projects of providers of housing and utility services. *Management of Development of Complex Systems*, 51.
5. Chernenko, Y. V., Semko, I. B. (2017). Peculiarities of management of development projects in engineering companies of the power distribution industry. *Bulletin of Cherkasy State Technological University*, 3, 52-56.
6. Danchenko, O. B. (2015). Methodology of integrated health care management in projects: dis. Dr. Tech. Sciences: 05.13.22. Kyiv: Ukraine. 347 p.
7. Bedrii, D. (2020). Development of a model of integrated risk and conflict management of scientific project stakeholders under conditions of behavioral economy. *Technology audit and production reserves*, Vol. 3, 2(53), 9-14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15587/2706-5448.2020.207086>.
8. Bedrii, D. (2020). Integrated anti-risk management of conflicts of a scientific project in a behavioral economics. *Scientific Journal of Astana IT University*, vol. 3, September 2020, 4-14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37943/AITU.2020.15.62.001>.
9. Kuzminska, Yu. M. (2019). Models and methods of forming teams of educational projects of professional development: autoref. thesis ... candidate technical Sciences: 05.13.22. Lviv: Ukraine. 21 p.
10. Danchenko, O. B., Kuzminska, Yu. M. (2012). The creative potential of the team as a factor of project success. *Project management and production development*, 3(43), 70-74.
11. Chernenko, Y., Haidaienko, O., Tkachenko, V. (2022). Development of a risk management method for development projects of providers of housing and utility services. *Technology Audit and Production Reserves*, 6/2(68), 27-33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15587/2706-5448.2022.269494>.
12. Simchenko N. O. (2010). Evaluation of the competence profiles of managers in the management hierarchy. *Economic bulletin of NTUU "KPI"*, 25, 126-132.
13. Kryvoruchko, O. M., Kovalyova, O. P. (2022). Assessment of corporate management competencies. *Economy of the transport complex*, 39, 45-54. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30977/ETK.2225-2304.2022.39.0.45>.
14. Halkiv, L. I., Kulinich, T. V., Sinkevich, K. V. (2021). Competency approach in project management of the organization. *Economy and the state*, 11, 20-25. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32702/2306-6806.2021.11.20>.
15. Timoshyk, V. (2019). Competency approach in evaluating the labor resources of the enterprise. *Galician Economic Bulletin*, 61, 6, 155-163. DOI: https://doi.org/10.33108/galicianvisnyk_tntu2019.06.155.